

USE OF IMPLICATURE IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: The article focuses on the study of the phenomenon of implicature in linguistics. The theoretical foundations and practical applications of the phenomenon of implicature, which is, part of pragmatics are considered.

Key words: implicature, pragmatics, speech situation, secret judgment.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена изучению явления импликатуры в языкознании. Рассмотрены теоретические основы и практические применения явления импликатуры, являющегося частью прагматики.

Ключевые слова: импликатура, прагматика, речевая ситуация, тайное суждение.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada tilshunoslikdagi implikatura hodisasini o'rganishga asosiy e'tibor qaratilgan. Pragmatikaning bir qismi bo'lgan implikatura hodisasining nazariy asoslari va amaliy qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: implikatura, pragmatika, nutqiy vaziyat, yashirin hukm.

Implicature is a concept that plays a crucial role in the field of linguistics. It refers to the meaning that is conveyed indirectly through a speaker's language use, rather than being expressed explicitly. Implicature is a powerful tool for communication, allowing speakers to convey meaning beyond the literal interpretation of their words. In this article, we will explore the use of implicature in linguistics.

The concept of implicature was first introduced by philosopher and linguist H. P. Grice in 1975. Grice argued that speakers often convey meaning indirectly through their language use, and that this indirect meaning is essential to successful

communication. He proposed that speakers follow certain conversational maxims, such as the maxim of relevance, which state that speakers should only provide information that is relevant to the conversation.

Grice also distinguished between two types of implicature: conventional implicature and conversational implicature. Conventional implicature refers to the meaning that is conveyed by a particular word or phrase, such as the word "but" indicating a contrast between two ideas. Conversational implicature, on the other hand, refers to the meaning that is conveyed through the context of the conversation, such as a speaker saying "I'm so cold" to indicate that they would like the window to be closed.

Implicature is a vital aspect of language use, as it allows speakers to convey meaning beyond the literal interpretation of their words. For example, a speaker might say "I don't have any plans tonight" to indicate that they are available to hang out, even though they did not explicitly say so. Similarly, a speaker might say "I'm not hungry" to decline an invitation to dinner, even if they are not actually full.

The use of implicature varies across cultures and languages, as different languages have different conventions for indirect language use. For example, in Japanese culture, it is common to use indirect language to convey politeness, whereas in American culture, direct language is often preferred.

Implicature is also relevant to fields beyond linguistics, such as philosophy and psychology. Philosophers have used Grice's theory of implicature to explore issues such as the nature of meaning and the relationship between language and thought. Psychologists have studied implicature in relation to cognitive processes such as theory of mind, which refers to the ability to understand the mental states of others.

There are many ways through which implicature can be expressed:

1. Irony: Irony is a form of implicature that involves saying something that is the opposite of what is actually meant. For example, saying "Great job!" when someone has actually done a terrible job is an example of ironic implicature. The

meaning of the statement is conveyed through the tone of voice and context in which it is said, rather than the words themselves.

2. Politeness: Politeness implicature is a way of communicating indirectly to avoid causing offense or disrespect. For instance, instead of saying "I don't like your shirt," one might say "That's an interesting choice of shirt." The latter statement implies a negative opinion but is less confrontational and more polite.

3. Sarcasm: Sarcasm is similar to irony in that it involves saying the opposite of what is meant. However, sarcasm is typically used to express contempt or ridicule. For example, saying "Oh, great. Another meeting" when a meeting has been scheduled is an example of sarcastic implicature.

4. Implicatures of quantity: Implicatures of quantity refer to the idea that speakers can convey meaning through the amount or degree of information they provide. For example, saying "I saw a dog today" implies that there was only one dog, whereas saying "I saw some dogs today" implies that there were multiple.

5. Implicatures of relevance: Implicatures of relevance involve conveying meaning through the relevance of the information provided. For example, saying "I'm going to the store, do you want to come?" implies that the speaker is going to the store and is inviting the listener to come along.

Here are some examples of implicature in daily speech.

1. "It's getting late, I should go."

This statement implies that the speaker wants to leave, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker does not want to overstay their welcome or inconvenience the other person.

2. "Do you want to come to my party tonight?"

This question implies that the speaker wants the other person to attend their party, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker values the other person's presence and wants them to be a part of the event.

3. "I'm sorry, I can't make it."

This statement implies that the speaker cannot attend an event or appointment, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker regrets not being able to attend and values the other person's time and effort.

4. "I'm not sure if I can help you, but I'll try."

This statement implies that the speaker is willing to help, even though they are not sure if they can. The implication is that the speaker values the other person's needs and is willing to make an effort to assist them.

5. "I'm not a big fan of seafood."

This statement implies that the speaker does not like seafood, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker has a preference for other types of food and may be hesitant to try seafood dishes.

6. "I love your new haircut."

This statement implies that the speaker likes the other person's new haircut, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker values the other person's appearance and wants to compliment them.

7. "I'm not feeling well today."

This statement implies that the speaker is sick or unwell, even though they did not directly say so. The implication is that the speaker may need rest or medical attention and may not be able to participate in activities as usual.

In conclusion, implicature is an important aspect of speech that allows speakers to convey meaning indirectly through their choice of words, tone of voice, and context. Understanding examples of implicature can help us to better understand the subtleties of language and the various ways in which meaning can be conveyed. Grice's theory of implicature has provided a framework for understanding this phenomenon, and its relevance extends to other fields such as philosophy and psychology. Understanding implicature is essential for effective communication, as it allows us to interpret the meaning behind the words we hear. It enables us to communicate in a subtle and indirect way, while still conveying important messages

and intentions. By recognizing and understanding implicature, we can better interpret the true meaning behind what is being said and respond accordingly.

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